

Coordination compound, derivative of isothiosemicarbazide of transition metals as an inhibitor of superoxide radicals

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Abstract. A new biologically active coordination compound, which belongs to the class of transition metal isothiosemicarbazides - bis (μ_2 -acetate-*o*)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazone-thioate] copper} dihydrate was obtained. It has established that this compound exhibits strong anti-radical properties to the action of the organic molecule with the superoxide radical. Due to this property, the obtained compound can have a wide application in medicine as an inhibitor of superoxide radicals in the human body, thus preventing damage to cells and tissues, atherosclerosis and carcinogenesis. The synthesized coordination compound expands the arsenal of superoxide radical inhibitors with high biological activity.

Keywords: superoxide radical inhibitors, coordination compounds, isothiosemicarbazide derivatives.

Координационное соединение, производное изотиосемикарбазида переходных металлов, как ингибитор супероксидных радикалов

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Аннотация. Получено новое биологически активное координационное соединение, относящееся к классу изотиосемикарбазидов переходных металлов - бис ((μ_2 -ацетато-*o*)-бис {[N-проп-2-ен-1-ил-N'-(пиридин-2-илметиллиден) карбамогидразонотиоат] меди} дигидрат. Установлено, что это соединение проявляет сильные антирадикальные свойства при взаимодействии органической молекулы с супероксидным радикалом. Благодаря этому свойству полученное соединение может найти широкое применение в медицине в качестве ингибитора супероксидных радикалов в организме человека, предотвращая, таким образом, повреждение клеток и тканей, атеросклероз и канцерогенез. Синтезируемое координационное соединение расширяет арсенал ингибиторов супероксид-радикалов, обладающих высокой биологической активностью.

Ключевые слова: ингибиторы супероксид-радикалов, координационное соединение, производные изотиосемикарбазида.

Introduction

Studies in recent years have provided increasing evidence that damage caused to cells by oxygen free radicals and nitrogen free radicals are the most important factors leading to aging and degenerative diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, cataracts, chronic inflammatory processes, renal failure, etc.[1-3]. The identification, study and testing of new remedies to correct disorders that occur as a result of the imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants, in favor of oxidants, having destructive and pathogenic potential in acute and chronic degenerative diseases (of the most common types of diseases), is of interest especially due to the increased incidence and severity of these pathologies.

However, there is a clear necessity for the development of new compounds, which could serve as a base for the development of medical preparations for the prevention and treatment of the mentioned above diseases.

The particular interest in this regard are thiosemicarbazide derivatives, which could exert a significant influence on the multiple free radical processes, which are forming in large quantities in many diseases and pathological processes.

Research over the last decade has revealed their therapeutic efficacy and their prospects for recovery [4-6].

At the same time, their mechanisms of biochemical action, especially on peroxidative processes, are not known in detail.

The aim of the study is to investigate the influence of new coordination compounds of copper, thiosemicarbazide derivatives on free radical oxidation processes, estimating and selecting the most effective compounds to combat diseases caused by excess of free radicals, and which can be used for prevention and treatment of acute and chronic degenerative diseases.

Respectively, one of the priority directions of modern applied chemistry is the synthesis of new compounds, which capture and neutralize superoxide radicals, thus preventing the development of cell and tissue damage, including inflammatory processes in the human body, atherosclerosis and carcinogenesis.

Material and methods

A new, biologically active, copper-coordination compound in the class of isothiosemicarbazides of transition metals - bis (μ_2 -acetate-o)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazone-thioate] copper} dihydrate, of formula (Scheme 1) has been investigated. This compound has been synthesized [5], at the State University of Moldova in the Laboratory "Advanced materials in biopharmaceutics and technics" but its influence on oxidative processes with ROS, such as superoxide radical, has not been studied.

The scavenging activity of the superoxide radical was determined by the spectrophotometric method, described in [7,8] with some modifications. This method is based on the generation of superoxide radicals by the reduced phenazine methosulfate / nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (PMS / NADH) system by oxidation of NADH, and the superoxide radicals reduce the tetrazolium salt - Nitro Blue Tetrazolium (NBT) in blue-purple formazane.

The method is carried out as follows: the working dilutions of the tested substances in DMSO solution in

concentrations 0,1; 1.0; 10.0; 100 μM / l were prepared. Then 20 μl of each working dilution of the tested substances into the wells of the 96-well microplate was pipetted. Each dilution was poured into duplicate. Then 180 μl of medium (working mixture) containing 20 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), NADH (0.1 mM) and NBT (0.09 mM) was added. The control sample was mounted in the same way as the test sample, but instead of dilutions of the tested substances, an equivalent amount of 20 mM phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.4) was poured. It has been prepared into duplicate. After mixing, the absorbance at 560 nm [A_0] was measured. Then, in all wells, 20 μl of 8.0 μM phenazine methosulphate (FMS) solution was added, was stirred for 10-15 s and was incubated at room temperature for 5 min, after which the absorbance [A_1] was remeasured at 560 nm. The percentage of superoxide radical scavenging was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Superoxide radical scavenging activity (\%)} = [(A_0 - A_1)/A_0 \times 100];$$

where A_0 is the absorbance of the control and A_1 is the absorbance of the tested compounds or the standard and / or reference substances.

Quercetin (3,3', 4,5,6-pentahydroxyflavone) and coordination compound bis (2,4,6-trinitrophenolate) bis (2,2'-pyridin-2,6-diyl-kN)-bis-1H-benzimidazole] - copper (II) bis (N, N-dimethylformamide) solvates were used as a standard and reference substances for the determination of superoxide radical inhibitory activity.

Quercetin (3,3',4,5,6-pentahydroxyflavone) with the formula:

is a natural flavonol which possesses antioxidant and antiinflammatory effects, destroys cancer cells, prevents cardiovascular disease [9,10,11].

Coordination compound bis (2,4,6-trinitrophenolate) bis (2,2'-pyridin-2,6-diyl-kN)-bis-1H-benzimidazole] - copper (II) bis (N, N-dimethylformamide) solvates of the formula (Scheme 1) is one of the synthetic chemical compounds with the highest antiradical activity described in the literature [12]:

Results and discussions

The compound bis (μ_2 -acetate-o)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazone-thioate] copper} dihydrate has anti-superoxide radical activity, with an IC_{50} of $0.35 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{M}$, which is 176.7 times higher than the activity of quercetin, used as a standard for the determination of superoxide radical inhibition activity and is 2.8 times more effective than prototype (Table 1).

The disadvantage of quercetin is that, it does not have a high antiradical activity [half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) is only $61.86 \pm 2.51 \mu\text{M}$ / L], as well as causing toxic side effects [11].

Scheme 1. The chemical structure of the compound bis (2,4,6-trinitrophenolate) bis (2,2'-pyridin-2,6-diyl-kN)-bis-1H-benzimidazole] - copper (II) bis (N, N-dimethylformamide) solvate [12].

Table 1. The anti-superoxide radical activity of the researched compound compared to quercetin and prototype.

Compound	IC ₅₀ , μM/L
Quercetin (3,3',4,5,6-pentahydroxyflavon)	61,86±2.51
Bis (2,4,6-trinitrophenolate) bis [2,2'-pyridin-2,6-diyl-kN)-bis-1H-benzimidazole]-copper (II) bis (N, N-dimethylformamide) solvate (prototype)	0,99±0.09
Bis (μ ₂ -acetate-O)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazonothioate] copper} dihydrate	0,35±0.07

From known synthetic chemicals, it has been established that in the case of bis (2,4,6-trinitrophenolate) bis [2,2'-pyridin-2,6-diyl-kN) -bis-1H-benzimidazole] -copper (II) bis (N, N-dimethylformamide) solvates (prototype) the half maximal superoxide radical inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) is = 0.99 ± 0.09 μM / L, which is 62.5 times higher than of quercetin. However, the given compound does not possess a sufficiently high superoxide radical inhibiting activity and has not been found wide application in medicine so far.

Established property of the compound bis (μ₂-acetate-o)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazonothioate] copper} dihydrate is new, because its use as an inhibitor of superoxide radicals has not been described so far.

Comparative analysis of bis (μ₂-acetate-o)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazonothioate] copper} dihydrate with prototype demonstrates that they differ, and they belong to different classes of copper (II) coordination compounds and a new combination of already known chemical bonds have been made in the investigated compound.

Scheme 2. Chemical structure of the compound bis (μ₂-acetate-o)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazonothioate] copper} dihydrate.

The process of obtaining of the above-mentioned compound is simple in execution, the starting substances are accessible [5]. The investigated complex is stable in contact with air, slightly soluble in water and aliphatic alcohols, is soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulfoxide, practically insoluble in ether. The conducted researches established that the investigated compound represents a coordination dimer, in which the elementary fragment represents a copper (II) complex with a distorted tetragonal-pyramidal structure (Scheme 2).

In the inner sphere of the central atom is a tridentate thiosemicarbazone molecule, which coordinates to the copper atom through the pyridine nitrogen atoms [d (Cu-N) = 2.059 Å], azomethine [d (Cu-N) = 1.970 Å] and sulfur atom in deprotonated thiol form [d (Cu-S) = 1,736 Å], forming two metallocycles of five atoms. The double bond in the coordinated isothiosemicarbazone molecule is delocalized between the carbon and nitrogen atoms N⁴ [d(C³ - N⁴) = 1,337Å] and carbon and nitrogen azot N³ [d(C³ - N³) = 1,334Å]. The fourth and fifth places in the inner sphere of the copper atom are occupied by two oxygen atoms of acetate ions with distances d¹ (Cu-O) = 1,954Å and d² (Cu-O) = 2,429Å. In the outer sphere of the complex dimer there are two molecules of water of crystallization, which form hydrogen bonds with the coordination dimer. Other interatomic distances and valence angles are standard for compounds in this class.

Thus, based on the results of the element analysis, the physico-chemical research and the X-ray analysis, the composition and structure of the investigated compound has been established.

Use of a novel coordination compound - bis (μ₂-acetate-o)-bis {[N-prop-2-en-1-yl-N'-(pyridin-2-ylmethylidene) carbamo-hydrazonothioate] copper} dihydrate expands the arsenal of compounds with high superoxide radical inhibitory activity.

Direct quantitative measurement of the superoxide radical (O₂⁻) is difficult due to its exceptional reactivity

and short half-life. The most commonly used in biological and chemical systems are the classical methods that use the PMS / NADH NBT system and that allow to determine the activity of superoxide radical scavenging.

As mentioned above, repeated exposure to these radicals is considered a major cause of aging, neurodegenerative and inflammatory diseases due to the gradual deterioration of major cellular components, such as DNA and proteins. In pathogenic process of acute and chronic degenerative diseases (the most common diseases) an important role is being attributed to reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS / RNS), in particular, the superoxide radical, which from a biological view, can be generated from two major sources: mitochondrial respiratory chain and NADPH oxidase (nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate oxidase) - an enzyme complex found in the plasma membrane, as well as in the membranes of phagosomes of nucleate polymorphic leukocytes of the blood to destroy microorganisms [13].

However, the superoxide radical $O_2^{\cdot-}$ is the product of the mitochondrial respiratory chain and a crucial component of the immune system. Due to high reactivity of superoxide radicals $O_2^{\cdot-}$ - through their potential to oxidize nucleic acids, proteins, lipids or carbohydrates, they are responsible for multiple harmful actions

in the body, such as inflammation, cancer, cardiovascular disease, hypertension, ischemia /reperfusion, diabetes mellitus, neurodegenerative diseases (Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease), rheumatoid arthritis, alcohol-induced liver disease, ulcerative colitis, senescence and atherosclerosis. Antioxidants through their ability to eliminate free radicals (FR) present in biological systems from a wide variety of endogenous and / or exogenous sources, limit the harmful effects of FR, allowing the body to fight efficiently in various pathological situations, limiting the injuries, and do not allow their spread [14 -16].

Therefore, the therapeutic inhibition of the superoxide radical is a new contribution, because the compounds with antiradical activity show a strong curative effect, thus preventing multiple harmful actions in the body.

Further studies have to confirm the therapeutic utility of this bioactive compound under investigation.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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